

***s*-DI-*m*- AND -*p*-TOLYLTHIOVIOLURIC ACIDS AS REAGENTS FOR GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF METALS AND FOR SALTS OF ORGANIC BASES**

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s-Di-*o*- and -*p*-tolylthiovioluric acids have been found to be good reagents for the gravimetric estimation of silver, ferrous and uranyl ions and for the preparation of salts of organic bases.

Though much work has been done with the alkali salts of violuric acid (Hartley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1797; Hantzsch, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 966; Meek and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 544) from the point of view of colour and chemical constitution, no work appears to have been done on *s*-di-*m*- and -*p*-tolylthiovioluric acids for their application in the gravimetric estimation of metals and for the preparation of their organic salts. The present paper is the outcome of an attempt to study the use of the above substituted thiovioluric acids in the gravimetric estimation of silver, ferrous iron and uranyl ions and in the preparation of highly coloured salts of organic bases.

The substituted thiovioluric acids exist in tautomeric forms—oximino ketonic (I) as well as nitroso-enolic (II), as represented below.

The compound represented by formula (I) is a fairly strong acid of monobasic character and the hydrogen atom marked by an asterisk is capable of being replaced by metals. The -CO- group in position 6 is really the residue of a carboxyl group and its carboxylic (acidic) character is enhanced by the presence of tolyl groups in the molecule, which reduces the basicity of N. Therefore the metals easily replace the labile hydrogen atom of the molecule. Such metal salts are stabilised by intramolecular co-ordination.

When such a -CO- enolises by the transference of the labile hydrogen atom, it becomes as much acidic in character as a carboxyl, and therefore more so than an -N.OH group. The nitroso-enolic form forms salts with organic bases which are highly coloured

in accordance with the observations of Hantzsch *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), who have shown that the greater the basic nature of the alkali or alkaline earth used in the salt formation with violuric acid, the greater is the intensity of the colour of the corresponding salt thus formed. It will be clear from the results recorded in this paper that the greater is the basic character of the organic base, the greater in general is the production of colour.

EXPERIMENTAL

s-Di-m-tolylthiobarbituric Acid.—A mixture of *s-di-m-tolylthiourea* (100 g.), malonic acid (60 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (80 g.) was powdered and heated with acetyl chloride (120 c.c.) for 1 hour at 80°. The solid was washed with boiling water to remove unchanged malonic acid, filtered, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow crystals, m.p. 245°, yield 65%. (Found: N, 8.72; S, 9.9. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 8.65; S, 9.89%).

s-Di-p-tolylthiobarbituric Acid.—A mixture of *s-di-p-tolylthiourea* (100 g.) malonic acid (50 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (80 g.) was powdered and placed into a r. b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser with acetyl chloride (140 c.c.). The mixture was heated at 85° for 1 hour. The residue was filtered, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 218°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 8.70; S, 9.84. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 8.65; S, 9.89%).

s-Di-m-tolylthiovioluric Acid.—*s-Di-m-tolylthiobarbituric acid* (80 g.) was dissolved in 15% KOH (200 c.c.) and after treatment with sodium nitrite (80 g.), dissolved in the minimum amount of water, was treated with a little excess of dilute H_2SO_4 . The product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in orange-red form, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 12.01; S, 9.09. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 11.9; S, 9.08%).

s-Di-p-tolylthiovioluric Acid.—*s-Di-p-tolylthiobarbituric acid* (40 g.) was dissolved in 20% KOH (150 c.c.) and treated with a solution of sodium nitrite (40 g.), dissolved in the minimum amount of water. The mixture was cooled to 0° and to this dilute H_2SO_4 was added in a little excess with stirring. On keeping overnight a brick-red precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in orange-red needles, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 11.97; S, 9.02. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 11.9; S, 9.08%).

Inorganic Salts of s-Di-m-tolylthiovioluric Acid.—To a known volume of the standard solution of the metallic salt (vide Table I), a 2% solution of *s-di-m-tolylthiovioluric acid* in acetone was added. The precipitated metallic derivative was filtered into a weighed Gooch crucible, washed with acetone and dried. From the weight of the precipitated metallic salt, the amount of the metal present in it was calculated. From the weight of the metal present in the original solution, the percentage of the metal precipitated from the solution by the reagent was calculated. The properties and data of the various inorganic salts precipitated are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Metallic salt	Weight of salt.	Weight of derivative.	Colour.	M.P.	% Metal ppted.
Silver nitrate	0.3236 g.	0.8736 g.	Green	243°	99.6
Lead nitrate	0.3884	0.3360	Yellow	220°	30.4
Copper sulphate	0.2490	0.1672	Brown	209°	21.8
Cadmium iodide	0.4894	1.4738	Yellow	192°	34.5
Ferrous ammonium sulphate	1.0066	1.9330	Bluish green	205°	99.2
Ferric alum	0.5060	0.2944	Green	210°	27.4
Zinc sulphate	0.1168	0.2126	Pale green	212°	68.0
Lithium sulphate	0.2466	0.2810	Yellow	177°	38.4
Cerous sulphate	1.0224	0.4958	Orange-yellow	189°	11.2
Vanadium pentoxide	0.1720	0.8816	Yellow	185°	25.8
Uranyl acetate	0.2018	0.4602		180°	99.3

Inorganic Salts of s-Di-p-tolylthiovioluric Acid.—The salts of the metals with s-di-p-tolylthiovioluric acid were obtained as in the previous case and the percentage of the metal precipitated from the solution by the reagent was calculated. The properties and data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Metallic salt.	Weight of salt.	Weight of derivative.	Colour.	M.P.	% Metal ppted.
Silver nitrate	3.3000 g.	8.9130 g.	Green	175°	99.7
Lead nitrate	3.3120	2.8440	Brown	178°	31.2
Copper sulphate	1.8640	1.2840	"	208°	22.4
Mercuric chloride	0.4140	0.2516	Orange-red	158°	18.2
Cadmium iodide	1.0290	0.7514	Yellow	195°	35.6
Bismuth chloride	1.0420	1.0480	Brown	228°	24.5
Ferrous ammonium sulphate	0.9539	1.8340	Green	203°	99.6
Ferric alum	0.5048	0.3015	Brown	206°	28.6
Nickel sulphate	1.3410	0.4455	Dark brown	258°	11.4
Cobalt nitrate	1.2000	0.5692	Chocolate	216°	18.2
Zinc sulphate	1.4280	2.7660	Brown	228°	71.4
Barium chloride	0.9275	0.5164	"	202°	16.1
Strontium chloride	1.4230	0.2241	Pink	190°	8.4
Magnesium sulphate	1.7560	0.4195	Brown	198°	8.1
Lithium sulphate	2.2540	2.5510	"	203°	36.2
Vanadium pentoxide	0.3640	1.0350	Pink	178°	26.8
Cerous sulphate	1.9250	0.4190	Green	202°	9.8
Uranyl acetate	0.4708	1.0770	Orange	216°	99.6

Organic Salts of s-Di-m- and -p-tolylthiovioluric Acids.—The organic salts of s-di-m- and -p-tolylthiovioluric acids were obtained by mixing equimolecular proportion of the respective thiovioluric acids with primary aromatic amines in alcoholic solution and refluxing at 50-60° for 3 hours. By slowly evaporating the alcoholic solution, coloured thioviolurates were obtained. Their characteristics are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Amine.	<i>s</i> -Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl.			<i>s</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl.				
	Colour.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.		Colour	M.P.	% Nitrogen	
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
Aniline	Brown	80°	12.62	12.55	Yellow	105°	12.50	12.55
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Green	78°	12.20	12.17	Pink	79°	12.22	12.17
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	Yellow	79°	12.22	12.17	Brown	72°	12.23	12.17
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	„	80°	12.25	12.17	Green	82°	12.20	12.17
α -Naphthyl-amine	Brown	80°	11.32	11.29	Violet	84°	11.32	11.29
β -Naphthyl-amine	Yellow	79°	11.34	11.29	Pink	78°	11.27	11.29

Thus *s*-di-*m*- and -*p*-tolylthiovioluric acids have been found to be good reagents for the quantitative estimation of silver, ferrous and uranyl ions and for the formation of coloured salts of organic bases.

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